

James Webb

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“For it takes only one well-established failure to rule out a model, but many successes to make a convincing case that a cosmology really is on the right track.” [1]
Principles of Physical Cosmology. P.J.E. Peebles.

1 Abstract

The key hypothesis of the Big Bang theory is the interpretation of the red-shifting of light coming from Galaxies given by the expansion of the universe and correlated with their brightness.

The James Webb telescope discovered two Galaxies, JADES-GS-z14-0 and JADES-GS-z14-1, which should be at the same distance from us, according to the interpretation of the redshifting by the Big Bang theory, but their brightness differs with a factor of 100! This is a big discrepancy which cannot be explained by the expansion of the universe.

Also, we will see that there is a large dispersion of the redshifting on photons issued from the same galaxy, which is also impossible with the expansion of the Big Bang theory.

In this paper we will propose a natural source of the red-shifting for light coming from galaxies and we will be able to explain the difference in brightness of two Galaxies having the same value of redshifting and the dispersivity of this factor.

A first evaluation of the red-shifting by natural process has been done by Lyndon Ashmore [2].

2 Observability

Astronomers are measuring galaxies redshifting by measuring the shift of the emission of the Lyman- α line for hydrogen, which wavelength is 121.5668 nm. The measured Lyman- α break by the James Webb telescope for JADES-GS-z14-0 and JADES-GS-z14-1 is shown to be $1.85\mu\text{m}$ [3].

The calculated Big Bang distance is supposed to fit the distance obtained through the galaxy brightness, but unfortunately for the Big Bang theory there is a large discrepancy in brightness between the two Galaxies at z14, JADES-GS-z14-0 and JADES-GS-z14-1. This incoherence between the value of the redshifting factor z and the brightness has already been observed for galaxies with z=9 [4]. At this value of z=9 the difference in brightness is of a factor 10! Then a factor 100 at z=14 is coherent since the more distant is a galaxy the more discrepancy in the lost energy can occur if it is due to a dispersive phenomenon in energy lost.

Also, the emission of the Lyman- α line for hydrogen is very narrow, allowing to give a precise value for the wavelength. However, at reception by James Webb, it is no more a perfect line, meaning that there is a “dispersion” of the initial emission line in multiple reception lines. This dispersion" for JADES-GS-z14-0" goes from $1.85\mu\text{m}$ to $2\mu\text{m}$, which is very large starting from 121.5668 nm.

These two observations, the incoherence of brightness with the redshifting factor and the dispersivity of the emission of the Lyman- α line, are inconsistent with the Big Bang theory. Since, for the Big Bang theory, the redshifting is due to the universe expansion, all photons issued from a galaxy will have the same extension of their wavelength as they progress in the intergalactic space. There should not be any dispersion of the emission line of the Lyman- α , and the brightness should be the same at the same redshifting factor z . James Webb is exposing the real nature of light coming from galaxies and we will propose a way to explain these facts with a natural process for this redshifting.

3 Natural Red-Shifting of a Photon

Georges Gamow, one of the developers of the Big Bang theory, speak about the photon redshifting on which the Big Bang theory is based: “It is true that some physicists and astronomers prefer to believe the observed red-shift is not due at all to mutual recession of galaxies, but must be explained by some as yet unknown physical phenomenon causing the reddening of light which travel over large distances. However, except for the descriptive statement to the effect that “light quanta may get tired traveling such a long way”, no reasonable explanation of such reddening has as yet been proposed, and as a matter of fact, can hardly be expected on present ideas concerning the nature of light” [5].

The red-shifting was first interpreted by Hubble, using Doppler Effect, meaning that all Galaxies should move away from us all the faster than they are away. But this conclusion has been used by the General Relativity theory which proclaims that the universe is in expansion. In consequence, the redshifting is now interpreted by this mathematical theory and not by the Doppler Effect.

Before searching a phenomenon which could explain the red-shifting of light coming from Galaxies, we should start by explaining what the nature of light and the nature of the propagating medium are. It is clear that we don't know that much about these two nature, but seemingly this ignorance doesn't prevent speaking about the red-shifting with certitude. It is admitted that light is composed of energy quanta, called photons, which are supposed to be like a particle and like a wave at the same time. The energy of the quanta of the photon is supposed to be equal to $h\nu$, h being the Planck constant and ν the frequency of the wave.

The particle concept of the photon is still in discussion and it has been shown that the experiment which leads to the duality concept can be explained simply by the photon wave. Then, in the following we will not take the particle hypothesis concept as a hypothesis.

The real nature of the wave is considered to be an electromagnetic wave which can be described by Maxwell's equations. The medium in which it propagates is never cited in the Big Bang theory and is often called “vacuum” in the literature, not to use the prohibited term “ether”! Whatever it is called, it has the electromagnetic properties of permittivity and permeability, which characteristics permits to connect electromagnetic and dynamic forces.

The only object in nature we know which can interact and exchange energy with a photon is an electron. To explain the redshifting of Galaxies, it has been already made mention of the interaction of the photon with an electron in an atom, like in the Compton Effect or the Mössbauer Effect. But these two effects would lead to the diffusion of the photons on their way to the Earth and would prevent to look clearly at the Galaxies. The Mössbauer effect has been proposed by Lyndon Ashmore, but the electron is bounded in an atom [2].

We will suppose here that the redshifting is due to the encounter of a photon with free electrons in the intergalactic space, in which the photon loses some energy at each encountering, the electron being expelled from the photon trajectory, with no impact on the photon trajectory.

The physical characteristic of the electric field wave of a single photon has been shown by C. Meis to be like a monochromatic oscillating plane wave and which at its maximum of oscillation is equal to [6]

$$E_{max} = \xi\omega_k^2, \xi = \frac{\hbar}{4\pi ec}, \hbar = \frac{h}{2\pi}, \omega_k = \frac{c}{\lambda} \quad (1)$$

With h the Planck constant, c the speed of light, λ the wavelength. Then:

$$E_{max} = \frac{hc^2}{8\pi^2 ec \lambda^2} = \frac{hc}{8\pi^2 e \lambda^2} \quad (2)$$

An electromagnetic wave is also composed with a magnetic field and which is also given by C Meis as:

$$B_{max} = \sqrt{\varepsilon_0 \mu_0} E_{max} \quad (3)$$

In consequence, the force applied on an electron close to the photon trajectory is given by the Lorentz formula:

$$\vec{F} = e(\vec{E} + \vec{v} \wedge \vec{B}) \quad (4)$$

With \vec{v} the relative velocity between the photon and the electron, e the electric charge of the electron.

Since the speed of the photon is c , the velocity of the electron is negligible and the relative velocity is c , meaning that the magnetic force is quasi equal to the electric force in absolute value. To simplify calculations in the following, we will model the sinusoidal time variations of the electric field by a simple rectangular pulse with half the value of the maximum of the electric field above. The resulting force can be expressed by:

$$|F_{max}^{\vec{}}| = e\sqrt{2} \frac{E_{max}}{2} = \sqrt{2} \frac{hc}{16\pi^2 \lambda^2} \quad (5)$$

The coefficient $\sqrt{2}$ is there to render for both the electric and the magnetic fields.

This force will exert a high acceleration on the electron, which will be expelled from the photon trajectory, the electron taking with it an energy to the photon equal to its kinetic energy. The acceleration on the electron, at the maximum is:

$$\gamma_{max} = \sqrt{2} \frac{hc}{16\pi^2 m_e \lambda^2} \quad (6)$$

This leads to the maximum expelled velocity of the electron, supposing an interaction time $\delta t = \lambda/2c$:

$$|v_{emax}| = \frac{\sqrt{2}h}{32\pi^2 m_e \lambda} \quad (7)$$

The energy taken from the photon energy by the kinetic energy is then given by:

$$\delta e_{max} = \frac{m_e |v_{emax}|^2}{2} = \frac{h^2}{32^2 \pi^4 m_e \lambda^2} \quad (8)$$

From (8) and for a photon wave-length of 1μ , the energy lost is $= 4.82 \cdot 10^{-30} J$. This energy lost is very low compared to the photon initial energy, assuring that there will be probably no (or hardly any) deviation of the photon trajectory along the way to Earth.

The change in wavelength can be calculated by the reduction of energy of the photon, which is at the maximum of lost energy:

$$\frac{hc}{\lambda_2} - \frac{hc}{\lambda_1} = \frac{h^2}{32^2 \pi^4 m_e \lambda^2} \quad (9)$$

Solving this relation permits to calculate the maximum change in wavelength, assuming that $\lambda_1 \lambda_2 \sim \lambda^2$:

$$\delta \lambda_{max} \sim \frac{h}{32^2 \pi^4 m_e c} = 2.43 \cdot 10^{-17} m \quad (10)$$

It can be seen that the change in wavelength is independent of the current wavelength at the interaction. If we suppose that the maximum of energy is lost at each interaction, we get a number N of total interactions:

$$N = \frac{\Delta \lambda}{\delta \lambda_{max}} = \Delta \lambda \frac{32^2 \pi^4 m_e c}{h} \quad (11)$$

With $\Delta\lambda$ the total redshifting observed on a galaxy. For JADES-GS-z14-0 we get a number of interaction:

$$N = \frac{1.8510^{-6}}{2.4310^{-17}} = 7.610^{10} \quad (12)$$

It is important to note that the energy lost may not be at its maximum at each interaction, in consequence the increase in the wavelength is reduced and then the capture surface is reduced. This fact leads to increase the number of possible interactions along the path, and the distance in consequence.

To conclude from this part, the redshifting of light coming through the interstellar space is hypothesized to be due to the interaction of each photon with free electrons encountered in the interstellar space. Each time a photon encounters a free electron, close to the photon path, the photon will lose an energy which is at the maximum is given in (8). After an interaction with a free electron, the energy of the photon is reduced, which means its frequency ν is reduced too, since the photon energy is equal to $h\nu$. In consequence the wavelength of the photon will rise, since the speed of light is a constant c equal to $\frac{1}{\sqrt{\lambda\nu}}$. Then after many interactions with free electrons encountered the photon wavelength is redshifted.

4 Red-Shifting Distance

To calculate the distance of a galaxy knowing its redshifting factor, we need to know how many free electrons can be captured by a photon in its course to Earth. This requires the knowledge of the surface of capture of an electron by the electromagnetic wave of a photon. The volume of interaction of a photon has been demonstrated to be equal to λ^3 [6], but it will be too large to suppose the surface of capture to be λ^2 , since it is a polarized wave.

Indeed, a photon wave is polarized in the perpendicular direction of propagation. But in literature it is presented as if being oscillating in a plane without thickness! This is quite unnatural! We have to suppose that the wave has a certain width, but which is totally unknown actually! A contrario, the electron has a capacity to interact via its “classical radius”. The “classical radius” of the electron is defined as “a combination of fundamental physical quantities that define a length scale for problems involving an electron interacting with electromagnetic radiation” [7]. The classical electron radius r_e is given in literature as 2.8110^{-15} m, but it can be neglected by comparison to the photon wave width, as we will see in the following.

We will suppose that the width of the wave length is equal to λ/w , w being a parameter to evaluate. The surface of capture is then:

$$\sigma = 2\lambda\frac{\lambda}{w} \quad (13)$$

The factor 2 is there to take both the electric and the magnetic fields.

In theory, we could calculate the distance to the galaxy via the number of free electrons captured by a photon:

$$D = \frac{\Delta\lambda}{2\lambda\frac{\lambda}{w}\tau} \quad (14)$$

With D the total distance to the galaxy, $\Delta\lambda$ the total redshifting, $\delta\lambda_{max}$ the maximum energy lost, τ the density of free photons in intergalactic space. But as said just above the wavelength is varying after each interaction, then we can't calculate the distance with this simple equation. Nevertheless, we can have bounded values while taking the wavelength at the emission and at the reception to be a constant all over the trajectory.

Lyndon Ashmore has developed a way to make a quasi exact calculation, but we will just calculate here bounded values.

We are going to evaluate bounded values of the unknown parameter w of the width of the wave length, by assuming that the distance given in the Big Bang theory has been calibrated to be in coherence with the measured brightness of stars . Then we can approximate the width of the photon wave by equating this brightness distance D:

$$\frac{1}{w} = \frac{\frac{\Delta\lambda}{\delta\lambda_{max}}}{2D\lambda^2\tau} \quad (15)$$

For JADES-GS-z14-0 the wave length at emission is 121.5668 nm and the wavelength at reception is approximately 1.85 μm , and the supposed distance given by the brightness is 1.310^{26} m. We can have bounded values while supposing the wavelength at the emission and at the reception:

$$\frac{1}{w_{max}} = \frac{7.610^{10}}{2 * 1.310^{26} (0.12110^{-6})^2 0.1} = 0.2 \quad (16)$$

$$\frac{1}{w_{min}} = \frac{7.610^{10}}{2 * 1.310^{26} (1.8510^{-6})^2 0.1} = 8.5410^{-4} \quad (17)$$

In consequence this give the width of a photon wave which is in between 0.2λ and $\frac{\lambda}{1000}$. Such values are probably difficult to get but nobody may have had the idea to measure it, since there has been no need!

5 Conclusion

Following the words of P.J.E. Peebles above, and considering what the James Webb telescope has produced, “the most distant JADES-GS-z14-0 . . . a massive and bright galactic record breaker that existed just 300 million years after the Big Bang” [8], we may proclaim that James Webb has produced a well-established failure of the Big Bang “story”, enough to rule out the Big Bang theory.

With the process of interaction between a photon and a free electron, we are now in capacity to explain qualitatively both the differences in brightness of the two galaxies having the same redshifting and the dispersion in wavelength of the emitted *Lyman* – α from a single galaxy.

In the two cases the variability come from the fact that the energy lost at each interaction is not a constant and not equal for each photon trajectory and that the free electron density may not be a constant value in the universe, contrary to General Relativity theory which is supposing a homogeneity of matter in the universe.

In the process of redshifting proposed above, there are numerous parameters which are unknown and may always been unknown. Despite all of these unknown parameters, the proposed redshift is a natural process of the redshifting of photons from the galaxies in the universe, whereas the Big Bang is a mathematical process and is not enough to explain these two observed facts.

We can see that there is a lot of work to do to confirm the proposed process of redshifting above but this is what James Webb observations tells us.

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